

EBFMC25-OOP-17 · Seasonal Variations in Public Interest in Dermatological Conditions in Türkiye: Google Trends Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Google Trends is a widely used online analytics tool that provides insights into public interest in various topics by tracking search queries on Google. Given its ability to reflect realtime public interest, Google Trends has gained increasing attention in medical research, including dermatology (Sivesind, Szeto, Kim, 2021; Oh, Rootman, 2024; Kluger, 2019; Martinez-Lopez, Ruiz-Villaverde, Molina-Leyva, 2018). Understanding seasonal variations in public interest in dermatological conditions can provide insights into patient concerns and potential healthcare demands. This study aims to evaluate seasonal fluctuations in Google search trends for various dermatological conditions in Türkiye from January 2022 to January 2025.

Materials and Methods: Weekly search volume data for 10 dermatological conditions (eczema, psoriasis, pruritus, urticaria, acne, skin cancer, tinea pedis, hair loss, scabies, and melasma) were collected from Google Trends. The searches were conducted in Turkish, and weekly RSV values were recorded. Seasonal differences were assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test, and significant variations were analyzed for trends.

Results: Significant seasonal variations were observed in search trends for multiple dermatological conditions (Table 1). Pruritus, urticaria and tinea pedis searches were highest in summer, likely linked to increased heat and humidity (Grandhi, He, Semeno, 2017; Sasagawa, 2019). Scabies searches peaked in autumn and winter, aligning with seasonal outbreaks and increased indoor crowding (Liu, Wang, Chang et al., 2016). Hair loss searches showed a peak in autumn, consistent with known seasonal shedding patterns (Kunz, Seifert, Trüeb, 2009). Skin cancer and melasma-related searches were highest in summer, reflecting increased sun exposure concerns. Psoriasis searches were lower in winter but peaked in spring and summer, which contrasts with the general expectation that psoriasis would worsen during winter and autumn due to decreased sunlight exposure, colder temperatures, and low humidity leading to skin dryness (Jensen, Serup, Alsing, 2022). Our findings suggest that during winter, plaques are often concealed under closed clothing, but they become more visible in the summer, leading patients to seek more information.

Conclusion: Public interest in dermatological conditions fluctuates with seasonal changes. These variations may reflect disease prevalence, symptom exacerbation, and public awareness. Understanding such patterns can help dermatologists and family physicians anticipate patient needs, optimize educational efforts, and tailor treatment strategies accordingly. Further research is needed to explore the correlation between search trends and actual disease incidence.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Google trends, public interest, dermatology

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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